

Regeneration capacity of IR66 calli as influenced by different treatments.

Treatment	Regeneration ^a	
	Solid medium	Liquid medium
Control	16-35 (15)	16-35 (15)
L-proline : 0.1 mg/liter	Clusters of small plantlets without further growth	30-50 (100-150)
L-proline : 0.3 mg/liter	Clusters of small plantlets without further growth	30-50 (100-150)
L-proline : 0.5 mg/liter	No regeneration	No regeneration
L-proline : 1.0 mg/liter	No regeneration	No regeneration

^aFigures in parentheses are the number of regenerated plantlets per culture vessel.

same composition as that of the regeneration medium. Filter paper was used to transfer the spots to the liquid medium.

Untreated calli not only developed green spots slowly, but their regeneration capacity was also less than that of the treated calli (see table). Results were similar when we transferred untreated calli to liquid regeneration medium. We observed a very high frequency (30-50%, 100-150 plantlets per culture vessel) of regeneration capacity in calli treated with low concentrations (0.1 or 0.3 mg/liter) of L-proline and transferred to liquid medium. High proline-treated calli, however, failed to regenerate on either liquid or solid media. ■

Performance of Punjab CMS lines in Cuttack, India

S. B. Pradhan and P. J. Jachuck, Central Rice Research Institute (CRRRI), Cuttack 753006, Orissa, India

We grew cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines PMS1 A to PMS10 A from a wild abortive source and their isonuclear maintainers from Kapurthala, Punjab, in the field during 1991 dry season (DS) and wet season (WS). The experiment was part of a collaborative project with the Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, India. We recorded pollen sterility, spikelet sterility in bagged panicles, plant height, days to 50% flowering, and panicle exertion from unreplicated rows of 30 plants for each of the CMS and maintainer lines.

Of the 10 CMS lines, PMS3 A, PMS4 A, PMS5 A, PMS8 A, and PMS10 A were completely pollen sterile, had reduced white anthers, and did not set any seed in bagged panicles in either season (see table). PMS1 A was completely sterile during DS and PMS7 A was sterile during WS. PMS2 A, PMS6 A, and PMS9 A were unstable.

All CMS and maintainer lines were of medium duration. Most of the CMS lines flowered 2-4 d later, had shorter plants and poorer panicle exertion than their maintainers (see table), perhaps because of the influence of their cytoplasmic

Evaluation of Punjab CMS and maintainer lines at CRRRI, Cuttack, Orissa, India, 1991 DS and WS.

CMS or maintainer line	Pedigree of B line	Pollen sterility (%)		Spikelet fertility (%)		Plant height (cm)		Days to 50% flowering		Panicle exertion (%)
		DS	WS	DS	WS	DS	WS	DS	WS	
PMS1 A		100	76.0	0	21.4	74	59	105	92	64.3
PMS1 B	Phulpattes 72/Jaya	-	-	79.3	84.1	88	83	105	89	100
PMS2 A		95	15.9	2.8	77.6	74	117	106	96	84.3
PMS2 B	Phulpattes 72/ Mutant 15	-	-	79.9	82.6	89	121	105	93	100
PMS3 A		100	100	0	0	77	63	106	94	72.1
PMS3 B	Basmati Mutant	-	-	83.0	87.6	90	83	104	92	100
PMS4 A		100	100	0	0	77	67	109	103	77.5
PMS4 B	IR8/Sigadis//NS200	-	-	67.9	79.4	83	78	109	100	100
PMS5 A		100	100	0	0	67	80	110	105	79.8
PMS5 B	PB134/Pb 133	-	-	79.3	75.2	85	85	109	105	100
PMS6 A		81.7	70.8	20.4	24.0	71	76	111	106	97.2
PMS6 B	PB134/Pb 133	-	-	68.9	85.1	89	82	110	105	100
PMS7 A		75.7	100	30.4	0	71	62	111	104	73.6
PMS7 B	IR305-3-17-13/ IR661-1-140-3	-	-	74.0	80.9	88	78	107	102	100
PMS8 A		100	100	0	0	79	80	105	105	76.9
PMS8 B	IR747-82-6-3/ IR665-40-6-3	-	-	76.7	71.8	91	85	102	104	100
PMS9 A		71.3	70.0	10.9	10.4	90	76	106	103	83.7
PMS9 B	PAU169-49-3-1-1/ PAU29-295-3-28	-	-	85.5	84.9	94	84	102	103	100
PMS10 A		100	100	0	0	74	69	107	91	78.5
PMS10 B	RP2B-849	-	-	71.8	68.4	87	74	103	90	100

factor. CMS lines were free from major diseases and pests.

Stable PMS lines PMS3 A, PMS4 A, PMS5 A, PMS8 A, and PMS10 A may be useful in developing hybrid rice for

the shallow rainfed ecosystem of eastern India because of their semitall stature, stiff straw, and medium duration. ■